

Deliverable 8.6

ENJOI Final event in Brussels and Bologna

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Task leader: formicablu

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ENJOI - Engagement and JOurnalism Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication

This project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under Grant Agreement n°101006407
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QUALITY ASSURANCE

To ensure the quality and correctness of this deliverable, we arranged an internal review and validation process. The deliverable was drafted by the work package leader (formicablu). All partners contributed and reviewed the overall draft. Finally, the final version was submitted to the project coordinator for a final review and validation.

DISCLAIMER

This report contains original, unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. It builds upon the experience of the team and related work published on this topic. Acknowledgement of previously published material and others' work has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both. The views and opinions expressed in this publication are the authors' sole responsibility and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission and the Research Executive Agency (REA), that are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information here contained.

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PROJECT OVERVIEW

ENJOI (ENgagement and JOurnalism Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication) explored and tested engagement as a key asset of innovation in science communication distributed via media platforms, with a strong focus on journalism.

Through a combination of methodologies and in collaboration with producers, target users and stakeholders of science communication, ENJOI co-created and selected a set of **standards, principles and indicators** (SPIs) as a guide for journalists and science communicators, to enable them to perform their work with the highest quality and to meet the needs of users. The SPIs have been condensed into the **Manifesto** for Outstanding Open Science Communication (OOSC), and their definition has also been followed by the development of specific **tools** for journalists and content producers to assist them practically in their work. All that results from the deployment of a series of actions via Engagement Workshops (**EWs**), **Labs**, field and participatory research, evaluation and testing phases. ENJOI worked in four countries: Belgium, Italy, Portugal and Spain, considering different cultural contexts.

ENJOI has also built an **Observatory** as its landmark product to make all results and outputs available to foster capacity building and collaboration of all actors in the field. The ENJOI Observatory aims to provide useful insights, resources and tools to support science and generalist journalists in their work. The virtual platform has a very practical structure: Networking, where you can get all the information about the possibilities of networking (such as conferences or workshops) but also possibilities of fostering the birth of collaborative activities; Reference, a collection of all the literature and resources that can be useful for professionals in the world of science communication; and Toolbox, with the ENJOI tools, some of them are being validated and will be available soon, but we are also scavenging the world for useful tools that our colleagues can use. The Observatory, currently hosted within the project website, will evolve into an independent product bound to remain online and actively nurtured well beyond the project end. Furthermore, the ENJOI Observatory will be part of the [COALESCE](#) project, funded under the Horizon Europe scheme to build the European Competence Centre for Science Communication.

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1. SUMMARY

The ENJOI final event was crucial for communicating and disseminating the project results. The last phase of the communication and dissemination strategy entailed close communication and strengthening the bonds with key actors. Dissemination and communication were focused on maintaining stakeholders' engagement and preparing the ground for a long-lasting legacy from where future projects and initiatives could emerge and build up.

At the end of the project, the results were disseminated during two events inviting journalists, science communication practitioners, EC officers, the scientific community, and representatives of the quadruple helix stakeholders.

To maximise the impact of disseminating the project results, an **ENJOI Policy event** was organised in Brussels in October 2023, to engage and inform policymakers about ENJOI's results, outcomes and future steps.

During this event, the project outcomes were presented to all relevant stakeholders, with the opportunity to organise a collaborative and participatory session in collaboration with relevant partners, where the policy recommendations were discussed and finalised.

In November 2023, the two-day **ENJOI Final event** was hosted in Bologna to reinforce the ENJOI community in the Mediterranean area and discuss about engagement as a key asset of innovation in (science) journalism.

During both the final events, the public launch of the ENJOI Observatory as a reference platform for SPIs, Manifesto, guidelines, recommendations and practical tools for the realisation of OOSC.

This report describes all the details of the events organised.

2. ENJOI POLICY EVENT

How can policy shape great science communication? The ENJOI Policy Event revolved around this question.

In recent years, improving science communication and journalism to address global challenges such as health and pandemics, climate change and the advent of AI has become increasingly urgent. In the past three years, the European project ENJOI worked to define a set of Standard, Principles and Indicators (SPIs) of high-quality science communication and journalism. The ENJOI SPIs are the product of different actions - such as Engagement Workshops, Labs, field and participatory research, scientific literary review, evaluation and testing phases - that also led to the creation of the ENJOI Manifesto for an Outstanding Open Science Communication and the ENJOI Observatory.

These results can be used to help policy support a healthy science communication environment, effectively combating global challenges with good science communication and journalism. And this was exactly the main goal of the ENJOI Policy Event in Bruxelles.

We explored how European policy can help support excellence in science journalism and science communication more broadly.

Elisabetta Tola, ENJOI coordinator, presented the project's policy recommendations to help policy support a healthy science communication environment, effectively combating global challenges with good science communication and journalism. These recommendations, which soon will be available through the ENJOI final policy brief, revolved around some key principles such as engagement, inclusion, diversity, open science, and open access. Training and capacity building was also considered at the core of high quality science communication and science journalism.

Aleksandra Hebda, Policy Officer at the DG R&I of the European Commission, gave a keynote speech entitled "The state of the art - Open Science policy and the ORE (Open Research Europe Platform)". ORE is an open access publishing venue for European Commission-funded researchers across all disciplines, with no author fees.

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After the introductory sessions, a round table was aimed at bringing out insights and perspectives on the current status and future potential of the science communication field, thanks to four key stakeholders in the field of science journalism and communication: Gianpaolo Accardo, Co-founder, Executive Editor at VoxEurop and Co-founder and Chief editor of the European Data Journalism Network; Vitalba Crivello, Science Policy & Communication Expert at the European Science Media Hub, European Parliament; Mohamed Elsonbaty Ramadan, Vice President of the Public Communication Science and Technology Network (PCST); Daniela Ovadia, Science Journalist, FRONTIERS project, ERC-Science Journalism Initiative.

The second part of the meeting hosted a collaborative and participatory session designed to collect feedback, opinions, perspectives, critiques, proposals, and ideas from the participants. The purpose of this format is also to give the participants a glimpse of the methodologies implemented over the course of the project, increasing engagement and co-creation.

2.1 Agenda of the ENJOI Policy event

The poster features a teal header with the ENJOI logo (a pencil tip forming the letter 'I') and event details: 'ENJOI POLICY EVENT', '4 OCTOBER 2023', '10:30 - 12:30 CET', and 'BIP MEETING CENTRE, PLACE ROYALE 11, BRUSSELS'. A lightbulb icon is positioned below the header. The main title is 'Ethics, engagement and excellence: how can policy shape great science communication?'. The agenda is presented in a list format with time slots in teal boxes. A key icon is on the right side, and a person holding a megaphone is at the bottom. The European Union flag and 'Funded by the European Union' logo are at the bottom right. The footer has a colorful bar.

ENJOI

ENJOI POLICY EVENT

4 OCTOBER 2023
10:30 - 12:30 CET
BIP MEETING CENTRE, PLACE ROYALE 11, BRUSSELS

Ethics, engagement and excellence: how can policy shape great science communication?

10:00 - 10:30	Welcome coffee
10:30 - 10:40	Welcome and warm-up Michael Creek, <i>Stickydot</i>
10:40 - 11.00	ENJOI final results and recommendations Elisabetta Tola, <i>ENJOI Coordinator, formicablu</i>
11.00 - 11.10	Keynote: The state of the art - Open Science policy and the ORE (Open Research Europe Platform) Aleksandra Hebda, <i>Policy Officer, DG R&I, European Commission</i>
11.10 - 11.50	Round table Gianpaolo Accardo, <i>Co-founder, Executive Editor at VoxEurop and Co-founder and Chief editor of the European Data Journalism Network</i> Vitalba Crivello, <i>Science Policy & Communication Expert at the European Science Media Hub, European Parliament</i> Mohamed Elsonbaty Ramadan, <i>Vice President of the Public Communication Science and Technology Network (PCST)</i> Daniela Ovadia, <i>Science Journalist, FRONTIERS project, ERC-Science Journalism Initiative</i> Moderator: Elisabetta Tola, <i>formicablu</i>
11.50 - 12.20	Interactive session: what challenges do we face to embed great science communication in policy? <i>With the participation of the entire ENJOI consortium and a number of invited stakeholders, policy makers, funders and other key experts</i> Moderator: Michael Creek, <i>Stickydot</i>
12.20 - 12.30	Wrap-up - Road to COALESCE Joana Magalhães, <i>Science for Change</i>
12.30 - 13.30	Buffet lunch

 Funded by the European Union

The agenda can be downloaded [here](#).

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2.2 The place: where and when

The ENJOI Policy Event was held in Brussels, in a strategic venue close to the central station.

Day: 04 October

Time: 10.00 am - 1.30 pm

Place: BIP MEETING CENTRE - PLACE ROYALE 11, BRUSSELS

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With its flexible layout the Zinneke Room setting up could be configured for plenary session, round table discussion and interactive session.

Plenary

Round table setting up

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Collaborative and participatory session layout

The entire event was recorded and streamed.

The full video is available here: https://youtu.be/AY6rSIF1_40

ENJOI POLICY EVENT
4 OCTOBER 2023
10:30 - 12:30 CET
BIP MEETING CENTRE, PLACE ROYALE 11, BRUSSELS

Ethics, engagement and excellence:
how can policy shape great
science communication?

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ENJOI SciComm Community

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2.3 The people: who and why

Here below is the list of 29 people who registered for the ENJOI Policy event.

All of them belong to one of the following categories:

- Decision-makers
- Representatives from policy institutions
- Representatives from funding institutions
- Representatives from the media (both generalist and science journalists)
- Representatives from academy

The variety of skills in the group made it possible to gather interesting feedback to test and implement policy recommendations.

First name	Surname	Institution/Organisation/Foundation
Francesca	Conti	formicablu
Elisabetta	Tola	formicablu
Tanja	Salandin	formicablu
Kim	Barbé	Research Foundation Flanders - FWO
Michael	Creek	Stickydot
Karina	Matozinhos	Science for Change
Ingrid	van Marion	ULB
Gian-Paolo	Accardo	Voxeurop
Esther	Marín-González	FC.ID (cE3c/Ciências.Ulisboa)
Alexandre	Torres	Stickydot
Vitalba	Crivello	European Parliament
Mohamed Elsonbaty	Ramadan	Public Communication of Science and Technology Network (PCST)
Joana	Magalhaes	Science for change
Federico	Bastarolo	ProMIS (Mattone Internazionale IT)
Iwan	Groeneveld	Science Europe
Alexander	Halksworth	Science Europe
Liesbeth	Delvax	FWO
Ahmed	Ghareeb	Smart dots foundation NGO
Irina	Tiron	Research Executive Agency

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Stefano	Spinaci	European Parliament
Senne	Starckx	Sciencejournalist.be / EFSJ
Aleksandra	Hebda	European Commission
Marzia	Mazzonetto	Stickydot
Rosa	Arias	Science for Change
Annita	Petrides	London School of Economics and Political Science
Daniela	Ovadia	Center for Ethics in Science and Journalism
Elisa	Nelissen	KU Leuven
Jason	Pridmore	Erasmus University Rotterdam
Kenia	Fita Capdevila	EUFIC

2.4 The questions and challenge

The policy event focused on this central question: how can policy shape great science communication? The primary objective of this event was to put into practice the policy recommendations outlined in the [first policy brief](#), and updated incorporating all the findings from the ENJOI project.

ENJOI's work demonstrated that Southern European countries do not have the same access to resources, the same independence, and the same possibilities in the media and, in general, in the information environment of Northern countries. Some weaknesses concern, for example, the independence of the sources used or the diversity and adequacy of the expert voices. Another critical point regards the open science and the open access approach in the entire cycle of information production. Moreover, there is an increasing interest in the world of information towards making diversity and inclusion real values, through the development of policies, attitudes, and practices in the whole media ecosystem.

A number of specific recommendations were addressed and analysed during the event. These have been classified into five distinct domains.

1. **Engagement, inclusion, and diversity.** Diversity is the best peaceful weapon against polarisation and discrimination. Diversity is a fundamental theme and has become a need on several levels. First, the media should respond to the requests coming from diverse communities and cultures of their audience and bring them into the process of content production. They should listen to their readers or listeners and apply

diversity as a guiding principle and as an engagement strategy in the whole life cycle of information. One of the ways to do this is by adopting the lens of intersectionality: be sure that we understand exactly that it is more difficult for some people than for others to access information and to access in general the realm of science education and science communication. In this issue, a special place is deserved by local communities. There are lots of small communities that will never make big numbers, and yet they need someone to cut information for them. Therefore, we have to make sure that we give indication and measure impact even when we talk to small, marginalised communities. In this respect, the Enjoi final recommendation is to look at scaling replicability with a very careful eye. Another aspect where diversity and inclusion come into play concerns journalists themselves. At the level of the European Commission, for example, it would be important to have more science journalists involved in writing grant proposals and discussing the needs and the issues that concern their professional community.

2. **Open science and open access.** Transparency and accessibility of scientific data and results are values that we can no longer do without. Within ENJOI, there's a strong belief that the entire scientific process must be made open and accessible. That there should be open data by rule in any institution. To get an idea of the risks and damage associated with openness and transparency, think of what happened in Italy during the pandemic, when not even the most important institutions made data publicly accessible, leaving room for the creation of false news, false interpretations, and above all distrust of science itself. It's really important to keep working on transparency and maybe even force it by asking all the platforms to have a code for transparency or to make sure that they describe their process. The issue of Open Access to data and publications is an area in which the European Commission has already shown interest and commitment, taking a first step with the creation of the Open Research Europe (ORE) platform. The platform currently hosts results and publications related to European projects (Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe), for which it has implemented a completely transparent and free peer-reviewed publishing system. Moreover, it is possible to publish results even after the funding is finished. Also, after several years every publication now has an associated index, and the platform is associated with social media channels with a professional team that produces posts daily.
3. **Training and capacity building.** This point, as already mentioned, concerns journalism in general, not only science journalism. The starting point should be establishing a connection with journalism schools, most of which do not have any

science training in most countries. Besides this, it is important to provide lifelong high-quality training for journalists: especially when we're dealing with innovative environments and new technologies – something that easily happens in science – content and information producers need to learn how to deal with them at any stage of their career. Moreover, it is important to support mutual collaboration between journalists and researchers, to help them realise that they need each other to continue doing their job in the best possible way. Concerning professional training, it is important to focus on what AI cannot do, that is the interaction with the world of science on one side, and with the world of the citizens on the other side. For this to happen, the role of policy is to foster training and collaboration between all interested parties: universities should bring on board journalists who can be critical towards science, and researchers should be willing to change their way of doing research and doing science to be more effective for society, and to build the trust towards their work with the aid of journalists. Journalists, in turn, can bring societal issues so that scientists are aware of them and report about scientists' outcomes in light of the societal issues. Finally, we need journalists who understand science. To address critical topics such as the pandemic, the climate crisis, or the intrusion of AI into one's life in an appropriate and correct manner, journalists should be able to make them understandable to everyone. The first step, therefore, is that they understand the topics themselves, or at least that they are capable of interacting effectively with scientists and experts on the topic. Policy could be a critical game-changer in promoting training or even in supporting the recruitment of science journalists in the newsroom of non-specialized media.

4. **Sustainability.** It is one of the biggest issues all content and information producers have to deal with. It has to do with policy, economics, and culture, and it has direct consequences on the quality of the content produced. The need for economic support concerns all realities. In the case of smaller projects that lack structural funding, or independent media that struggle a lot because their funding possibilities are limited, the risk is that they end up looking for money in the private sector, where they have to deal with conflicts of interest which, in turn, penalise transparency. Having adequate financial support is vital in order to guarantee the correct process behind the production of content. Writing or talking about science topics is not a one-directional process that goes from scientists to journalists, to society, but needs a few back-and-forth interactions, which are expensive and time-consuming. This process is too often sacrificed and simplified to allow for a coarser production of content that prioritises quantity over quality: that's where (political and economic)

support for independent journalism can make the difference. Among the most common solutions for sustainability, there is membership, which is strictly connected with engagement.

5. The ENJOI Project has looked for **engagement** as one of the key assets for ensuring high-quality science journalism and found out that a community involved in the production of content for a media outlet is also a community that might be happy to support that particular media economically. There are several cases in which engagement was crucial in the survival of some investigative journalism outlets, and the same could happen for science journalism. Other solutions already in place are syndication (that is, produce content and then sell them to others), and the production of content for third parties from scratch (translations, copy editing, or a story). But, more and more big media outlets, or legacy media, have their own strategy and have begun to rely on cheap sources like press releases copied and pasted and so on. One solution to keep science communication and science journalism available to the public is to get funds from public money. Another solution is to ask for support from scientific institutions: make them understand that they need science communication to keep on doing their job in research. Moreover, it is important to inform policy-makers about the situation in which journals and media outlets live. Tell them that independent editors do not exist anymore, and that half of the contents published in daily newspapers are paid by someone who has an interest in covering that news, and finally that greenwashing and hiding inconvenient content is common practice.

After discussing these policy recommendations deriving from ENJOI's results, the policy event continued with a roundtable discussion. The roundtable, moderated by Elisabetta Tola, involved experts with various backgrounds in media, communication, and science journalism: Giampaolo Accardo (VoxEurop), Vitalba Crivello (European Science Media Hub), Mohamed Elsonbaty Ramadan (Public Communication of Science and Technology network - PCST), and Daniela Ovidia (Center for Ethics in Science and Journalism).

The discussion revolved around the following key points:

- The importance of training journalists to communicate scientific topics effectively.
- The need for cultural changes in science journalism, varying levels of political support across European countries, and the promotion of science communication in the Arab world through networking and collaboration.

- The crucial role of journalism in providing critical perspectives to science, particularly in universities.
- The challenges posed by the increasing role of AI in journalism, and the need to focus on tasks that machines cannot replicate.
- The innovation trends in science journalism, including cultural changes, varying political support across countries, and adapting to AI.

Two specific case studies were also discussed:

- The Frontiers ERC project. Frontiers focuses on the interaction between journalists and the world of science on one side, and the world of the citizens on the other side. The project aims to offer the science journalist community in Europe the opportunity to have fellowships and to spend quite a large amount of time (from three to six months) in a research Lab to acquire in-depth knowledge of a specific scientific field. The idea behind this is the so-called cross-pollination: having a journalist in a research lab or institution is a way to change the way science is done. The project will analyse and study with sociological tools what are the actual needs of the journalistic community, and the institution they will work with, and besides them also the needs of the society.
- The European Science Media Hub. Since 2019 the European Commission has set up a project called Science Media Hub, which contains training for European journalists, and offers them the opportunity to travel to Brussels, Strasbourg, or to any of the other member states. The main objective is to make them aware of the legislation and political actions taken by the European parliament. Some of the courses cover the topic of AI, others climate change, and others deal with the phenomenon of disinformation to improve the quality of science communication in general.

The first part of the policy event was live-streamed and is available here: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AY6rSIF1_40

A 3-minute recap video about the event is being produced, and will be uploaded on the ENJOI [YouTube Channel](#) before the end of December.

A live-tweeting session of the whole event was organised by formicablu (see section 4 of this document).

2.5 Co-creation: building recommendations

The second part of the meeting, moderated by Michael Creek from Stickydot, was a collaborative and participatory session designed to collect feedback, opinions, perspectives, critiques, proposals, and ideas from the participants. The purpose of this format is also to give the participants a glimpse of the methodologies implemented over the course of the project, increasing engagement and co-creation.

Starting from the critical issues presented during the first part of the workshop, the participants feed the discussions around the following key points:

General Journalism Training:

- Focus on the need for a broader perspective on journalism, not limited to science journalism alone.
- Highlight the lack of science training in journalism schools in many countries.
- Call attention to the necessity for lifelong, high-quality training for journalists, especially in new technologies and innovative environments.

Collaboration and Residency Programs:

- Stress the importance of establishing connections with journalism schools.
- Foster collaboration through programs such as ERC (European Research Council) focusing on residence programs, facilitating mutual cooperation between journalists.
- Notes the rarity of such programs and their significance in promoting innovative approaches.

Local Communities:

- Acknowledge the existence of small communities that may not generate large audiences but still require accurate information.
- Need to provide guidance and measure impact, even in interactions with small and marginalised communities.
- Advocate for scaling replicability with careful consideration.

Sustainability Challenges:

- Sustainability was identified as a significant challenge, particularly for smaller projects lacking structural funding.
- Concern about the challenges independent media faces due to insufficient support.
- Highlight the risk of seeking funding from the private sector, potentially

leading to conflicts of interest and compromising transparency.

- Encourages a meticulous examination of scaling replicability to ensure widespread effectiveness.

The collective effort underscored the multifaceted challenges in science communication, ranging from training and collaboration to sustainability. The call for policy changes and support for smaller, independent projects reflects the need for a comprehensive and inclusive approach to advancing science communication.

All the suggestions collected will feed the final policy brief of the project.

Collaborative and participatory session: collecting feedbacks

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Participants' discussion on resulting feedback

Open data should be mandatory to facilitate the access to science journalists (and open data are more independent)

The communication WP of EU projects should be evaluated also in the light of the CV of the person in charge, not only the scientific WPs

Develop a EU policy recommendation for science journalism and science communication to support the development of national strategies

The top-voted insight

3. ENJOI FINAL EVENT - OBJECTIVES AND TASKS

On November 16th and 17th, in Palazzo Pepoli, Bologna, the ENJOI final event was held. It was not only an opportunity for the partners to gather and discuss together all the results of the project, to reason about the conclusions and its future development, but also a way to bring together journalists from different backgrounds and experiences in this unique context, to discuss and actively learn, once again, from the new ideas and awareness that ENJOI has been able to bring out. This two-day event was a crucial opportunity to reinforce the ENJOI community in the Mediterranean area. The full ENJOI final event was live-streamed and is available on the project's [YouTube channel](#).

The first part of the ENJOI final event, held on November 16th, was entitled “Engagement and Journalism Innovation for outstanding open science communication”. Its goal was to present and discuss the main project's outcomes and results. **Elisabetta Tola, the ENJOI coordinator**, went through all the phases of ENJOI from the beginning: the engagement workshops, the Labs and the definition of the principles, standards and indicators of good science communication (SPIs). **Michele Catanzaro**, from the Asociacion Catalana de Comunicacion Cientifica in Spain, spoke in detail about the SPIs and the writing of the ENJOI Manifesto. Then, **Marco Boscolo** presented the ENJOI media landscape research and the ENJOI Observatory. **Anne Dijkstra**, from the University of Twente, presented her research carried on within ENJOI on the relationship between scientists and the media. The ENJOI co-creation process was also discussed during the event. **Michael Creek** from Stickydot and **Karina Matozinhos** from Science for Change presented all the main steps leading to the methodology developed to co-create and host the ENJOI Engagement Workshops and Labs in four countries (Italy, Spain, Portugal, Belgium). **Esther Marín** from the University of Lisbon presented the ENJOI tools for multiple target users deriving from the ENJOI Engagement Workshops and Labs. These tools are prototypes aimed at improving - practically - science communication and journalism for different stakeholders. Some of these are dedicated to teachers and schools, others are for generalist journalists who find themselves talking about science for the first time and others are accurate checklists for learning how to write in compliance with the SPIs defined by ENJOI.

Another critical point that was discussed concerned recommendations for policy-makers to make the presence of science and science communication more and more meaningful in the decisions at the European level and, thus, in the lives of citizens.

In this roundup of results, summaries and new insights, there was an **interactive, co-creation session** led by Michael Creek, in which participants were asked to write and

discuss together their take-home messages: what inspired them most about the project, what they think will serve them well in the future, and what needs to happen now that there is more awareness. Among the things that emerged were the central role of politics in the change of perspective required in journalism, the need to improve from the perspective of inclusion and diversity, and the curiosity to apply the principles of co-creation in the newsroom. The day ended with the presentation of the following crucial long-term goal: the [COALESCE](#) EU-funded project, which aims to create a European Competence Centre for Science Communication, which will host the ENJOI Observatory.

The second part of the ENJOI final event, held on November 17th, was entitled “**Innovation and Engagement on the Journalism Horizon**”. It was an **international, cross-border conversation** involving journalists with different experiences who shared their journey to understand, together, which are the right keys to promoting innovation and engagement in journalism. And, also, to change those aspects that make applying principles, standards, and indicators difficult in today’s (science) journalism. Which makes it difficult, in other words, to provide excellent service to readers. The day started with a keynote speech by Aron Pilhofer, who approached the topic of innovation from the perspective of a generalist journalist. Pilhofer emphasised the importance of defining innovation as a process rather than an object. For this reason, it is also crucial to define a metric that can measure innovation because there is no innovation if it is impossible to establish objective parameters to estimate it. Two roundtables followed, discussing new ways of approaching journalism that rewards collaboration, engagement and in-depth news and content selection. In the first roundtable, Stephane Horel (Le Monde, France), Alberto Puliafito (Slow News, Italy) and Zeynep Sentek (The Toxic Valley investigative project, Arena Climate Network, Turkey and Portugal) talked about "Making journalism through collaboration and engagement". The second roundtable was on "Diving into in-depth journalism", and saw the experiences of Raffaele Angius (Indip, IrpiMedia, Italy), Sofia da Palma Rodrigues (Divergente, Portugal), and Eva Rodriguez (Sinc, Spain). The event ended with a few case studies broadening the definition of journalism: Info.nodes and Marla by Davide Del Monte (Italy), Geneva Health Files by Priti Patnaik (Switzerland), Radar Magazine by Anna Violato (Italy), and Thin Ink by Thin Lei Win (Birmanian and Italy). These tales of independent and 'revolutionary' realities in today's journalistic landscape offered valuable insights on promoting engagement and innovation in journalism, with a strong focus on science journalism.

3.1 Agenda of the ENJOI Final event

DAY ONE

ENJOI Final Event. **Engagement and journalism innovation for outstanding open science communication**, November 16th.

The poster features a teal header with the ENJOI logo, event title, date, and location. The main body is a light teal background with a list of sessions. A 'Funded by the European Union' logo is in the top right. Illustrations include a lightbulb, a group of stylized figures, and a starburst graphic.

ENJOI ENJOI FINAL EVENT
Engagement and Journalism Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication

16 NOVEMBER 2023
Palazzo Pepoli Museum,
Via Castiglione 10,
Bologna

14:00 - 14:30 Registration

14:30 - 14:50 Welcome and introduction. The ENJOI pathway
Elisabetta Tola,
ENJOI coordinator,
formicablu, Italy

14.50 - 15.10 The ENJOI SPIs and the Manifesto
Michele Catanzaro,
Asociación Catalana de Comunicación Científica, Spain

15.10 - 15.40 The ENJOI Observatory.
Innovation, engagement and openness in science journalism
Marco Boscolo and Giulia Bonelli,
formicablu, Italy

15.40 - 16.00 Science, media relationship: research findings
Anne Dijkstra and Anouk de Jong,
University of Twente, Netherlands

16.00 - 16.30 Coffee break

16.30 - 17.00 The ENJOI co-creation process: what did we learn?
Michael Creek,
Stickydot, Belgium
Karinna Matozinhos,
Science for Change, Spain

17.00 - 17.20 Innovative tools for multiple target users, an ENJOI production
Esther Marín,
FCiências.ID, Associação para a Investigação e
Desenvolvimento de Ciências, Portugal

17.20 - 17.40 Recommendations for an Outstanding Open Science Communication
Elisabetta Tola,
formicablu, Italy

17.40 - 18.10 What will you take from the ENJOI project?
Moderated by Michael Creek,
Stickydot, Belgium

18.10 - 18.30 What next? ENJOI and COALESCE
Joana Magalhães,
Science for Change, Spain
Elisabetta Tola,
formicablu, Italy

Funded by the European Union

ENJOI FINAL EVENT

The agenda can be downloaded [here](#) (PDF, 337 KB)

ENJOI - ENgagement and JOurnalism Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication

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DAY TWO

ENJOI Final Event. **Innovation and engagement on the journalism horizon**, November 17th.

The poster features a teal header with the ENJOI logo and event title. An orange circle in the top right corner contains the date and location. The main body is yellow with a list of activities in teal boxes. A stylized graphic of a hand holding a pencil is in the top right, and a starburst graphic with the event name is in the bottom right. The European Union logo and funding information are in the bottom left.

ENJOI ENJOI FINAL EVENT
Innovation and engagement on the journalism horizon

17 NOVEMBER 2023
Palazzo Pepoli Museum,
Via Castiglione 10,
Bologna

9:00 – 9:30 Registration

9:30 – 9:40 Welcome from the ENJOI Coordinator
Elisabetta Tola - *formicablu*

9.40 - 10.20 Innovation and sustainability in journalism today
Aron Pilhofer, James B. Steel Chair in Journalism Innovation, Temple University

10.20 - 10.40 Q&A with Aron Pilhofer
Moderator: Giulia Bonelli - *formicablu*

10.40 - 11.10 Roundtable 1, Making journalism through collaboration and engagement
Stephane Horel - *Le Monde, France*
Alberto Puliafito - *Slow News, Italy*
Zeynep Sentek - coordinator of The toxic Valley investigative project and director of the Arena Climate Network, Turkey and Portugal
Moderator: Karinna Matozinhos - *Science for Change*

11.10 - 1.40 Coffee and networking

11.40 - 12.10 Roundtable 2, Diving into in depth journalism
Raffaele Angius - *Indip, IRPImedia, Italy*
Sofia da Palma Rodrigues - *Divergente, Portugal*
Eva Rodriguez - *SINC, Spain*
Moderator: Michele Catanzaro - *Asociación Catalana de Comunicación Científica*

12.10 - 12.20 Broadening the definition of journalism. A few stories
Moderator: Marco Boscolo - *formicablu*

12.20 - 12.30 Info.nodes and Marla. Between activism and journalism
Davide Del Monte - *Italy*

12.30 - 12.40 Geneva Health Files. Health information in your mailbox
Priti Patnaik - *Switzerland*

12.40 - 12.50 Radar. A new look to environment
Anna Violato - *Italy*

12.50 - 13.00 Thin Ink. Deep into the food world
Thin Lei Win - *Birmania, Italy*

13.00 - 13.30 Wrap up
Elisabetta Tola - *formicablu*

Funded by the European Union

ENJOI FINAL EVENT

The agenda can be downloaded [here](#) (PDF, 217 KB)

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3.2 The place: where and when

The Final Event took place November 16th and 17th in the very city centre of Bologna:

The event, spanning over two days, was arranged as follows:

DAY ONE: November 16th

Time: 14.30 - 18.30

Place: Palazzo Pepoli, Via Castiglione 10, Bologna, Italy

DAY TWO: November 17th

Time: 9.30 - 13.30

Place: Place: Palazzo Pepoli, Via Castiglione 10, Bologna, Italy

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The ENJOI Final was held at Palazzo Pepoli, the Museum of the City History dedicated to the culture and transformation of the city over the centuries, from Etruscan Felsina to the present day.

Palazzo Pepoli, home to the Museum of the History of Bologna

The museum hall

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The event room: Sala della Cultura

The local community's history is innovatively told through an engaging itinerary with scenic and interactive exhibition techniques that immerse visitors in various rooms. Among multimedia panels and illustrated graphics, the palace houses precious archaeological finds, such as the Felsina burial from Tomb 10 of the Giardini Margherita, discovered in 1986, and great works of art by Guercino, Carracci, and Giacomo Balla.

A final guided tour was arranged for speakers and project partners after the two-day event.

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The entire event was documented and live-streamed on the ENJOI [YouTube Channel](#):

Streaming DAY ONE, November 17th: <https://youtu.be/bByxbQjKm14>

Streaming DAY TWO, November 17th: <https://youtu.be/GfWFW7jT1N0>

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3.3 The people: who and why

DAY ONE, participants

The project's achievements and results took centre stage on November 16th. The participants of November 17th (day two) were also extended an invitation to join, and those who had arrived in Bologna before the event's commencement were able to attend (9 out of 13 speakers).

In total, 25 people registered and **27 were in attendance.**

First name	Surname	Institution
Francesca	Conti	formicablu srl
Tanja	Salandin	formicablu srl
Giulia	Bonelli	formicablu srl
Anne	Dijkstra	University of Twente
Inês	Navalhas	FCiencias.ID/University of Lisbon
Karinna	Matozinhos	Science for Change
Anna	Violato	RADAR Magazine
Eva	Rodriguez Nieto	Agencia SINC
Stéphane	Horel	Le Monde
Zeynep	Sentek	Arena for Journalism in Europe
Sofia da Palma	Rodrigues	DIVERGENTE
Michele	Catanzaro	freelance, ACCC
Priti	Patnaik	Geneva Health Files
Andrea	Pracucci	formicablu srl
Anouk	de Jong	University of Twente
Esther	Marín-González	FCiências.ID (Ciências/ULisboa)
Cristina	Luis	CIUHCT, Faculdade de Ciências, Universidade de Lisboa
Davide	Del Monte	info.nodes
Valentina	Guglielmo	Istituto nazionale di astrofisica
Joana	Magalhães	science for change
Elisabetta	Tola	formicablu srl

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Marzia	Mazzonetto	Stickydot
Michael	Creek	Stickydot
Miriam	Rivera	Associació Catalana de Comunicació Científica (ACCC)
Tiago	Alves Costa	Quiasmo magazine

DAY TWO, participants

The second day consisted of a public gathering that brought together various stakeholders: individuals invested in science communication, journalism, and science journalism, students from schools of journalism (University of Parma), science communicators, representatives from academia, as well as the ENJOI Consortium as a whole.

The ENJOI coordinator, Elisabetta Tola, formicablu, asked the Local Press Association - a professional, strongly regulated entity - to recognise this event for credits.

As a result, **16 journalists** joined the event on November 17th.

Overall **63 professionals took part** in day two.

First name	Surname	Institution
Hariharan	Arevalagam	Rhine-Waal University of Applied Sciences
Anne	Dijkstra	University of Twente
Francesca	Conti	formicablu/journalist
Inês	Navalhas	FCiências.ID/University of Lisbon
Tanja	Salandin	formicablu
Marie-Christine	Thurm	EUFIC
Anna	Violato	RADAR Magazine
Eva	Rodriguez Nieto	Agencia SINC
Alberto	Puliafito	Slow News
Stéphane	Horel	Le Monde
Anouk	de Jong	University of Twente
Zeynep	Sentek	Arena for Journalism in Europe
Lisa	Lazzarato	formicablu
Stavroula	Pagkrati	Freelancer
Vânia	Maia	Freelancer / Lusófona University
Michele	Catanzaro	Science journalists / ACCC

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Priti	Patnaik	Geneva Health Files
Andrea	Pracucci	formicablu
Giuseppe	Nuzzi	InCronaca
Bianca	Bettio	InCronaca
Felice	Simeone	National Research Council (CNR)
Esther	Marín-González	FCiências.ID (Ciências/ULisboa)
Davide	Del Monte	Info.nodes / journalists
Valentina	Guglielmo	National Institute of Astrophysics (INAF) / science journalist
Joana	Magalhães	Science for Change
Elisabetta	Tola	Formicablu / science and data journalist
Cristiano	Spadoni	Image Line srl - magazine AgroNotizie.it / journalist
Karina	Matozinhos	Science for Change /journalist
Marzia	Mazzonetto	Stickydot srl
Chiara	Putignano	InCronaca (Master in giornalismo Unibo)
Tiago	Alves Costa	Quiasmo Magazine
Michael	Creek	Stickydot
Selvaggia	Santin	CMCC Foundation
Miriam	Rivera	Associació Catalana de Comunicació Científica (ACCC)
Marco	Malaspina	National Institute of Astrophysics (INAF) / science journalist
Callum	High	N/a
Valentina	Bazzarin	Professor of Cognitive Psychology at USAC, Lecturer at Master COSE University of Parma
Vittoria	Saraceni	University of Bologna
Elisabetta	Orfei	University of Bologna
Fabrizio	Lisi	University of Bologna
Eleonora	Tosi Brandi	University of Bologna
Andrea	Antonelli	University of Modena and Reggio Emilia
Aron	Pilhofer	Temple University
Raffaella	Agostini	Journalist
Raffaele	Angius	Investigative journalist
Sofia	Belardinelli	Journalist
Barbara	Benini	Journalist
Marco	Boscolo	Science journalist
Vittorio	Martone	Journalist

Gabriella	Ruffini	Journalist
Angela	Simone	Journalist
Antonietta	Torchi	Journalist
Alice	Facchini	Journalist
Jonathan	Ferramola	Journalist
Marina	Nasi	Journalist
Barbara	Pinelli	Journalist
Luca Francesco	Basile	Journalist
Giulia	Balestra	Journalist
Vittoria	Saraceni	Journalist
Gaia	Giorgi	Journalist
Andrea	Carboni	Journalist
Cristina	Lusi	Journalist
Lino	Greco	Videomaker and photographer

The event on November 17th also partnered with the local journalistic network (*Ordine dei Giornalisti dell'Emilia-Romagna*). Journalists who are network members could enrol and receive 4 training credits by participating in the event. This was also a significant opportunity to connect the ENJOI international community with the local journalists in Bologna.

3.4 Engagement and innovation: take home messages

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Here is a first recap of the main take-home messages revolving around engagement and innovation, the two main pillars explored during the ENJOI event:

- **Innovation.** In (science) journalism, innovation should be considered a “state of mind”. We often talk about innovation as a thing, as a technology, as a product. But we should talk of innovation as an evolutionary process, often an incremental process, that moves you gradually from something good to something better. This means that innovation can be applied not only to technology but also and especially to processes, including the human side of journalism.
- **Engagement.** Co-creation works on the principle of “nothing about us without us”. So anyone affected by a decision or an issue should be around the table to discuss it. This kind of engaged (science) journalism, rather than thinking of the public as sort of the recipient of journalism, needs to make the public the driver of journalism.
- **Collaboration.** In Europe, there are more and more projects where journalists collaborate with other experts, like scientists, especially in the climate journalism field. This needs to happen in a more structured way, for example, with training opportunities and grants that bring journalists and scientists together.
- **Inclusion.** Diversity (of sources, languages, styles, etc.) is a driving principle for high-quality (science) journalism. But diversity also means including diverse people in the newsroom: more people with different backgrounds, different cultures, different genders, and different approaches.
- **Sustainability.** There is an urgency for a much deeper conversation about how we can really solve the funding problem for independent media in Europe. There is a kind of dilemma between legacy media which have the resources and the fame to carry out innovations but often do not innovate, and startups or small, independent media that are applying innovative strategies but struggle to survive.

The ENJOI’s methodology and results, as well as the main insights deriving from the ENJOI Final Event, will be included in the ENJOI Observatory, as well as in the future COALESCE European Competence Centre for Science Communication.

4. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

The dissemination strategy developed during the ENJOI policy event (Brussels, October 4 2023) and ENJOI final event (Bologna, November 16-17, 2023) was a multifaceted approach aimed at maximising reach, fostering participation, and amplifying the impact of the events.

The strategy embraced a participant-centric approach, recognising the key role of engagement - which was explored within ENJOI as a key asset of innovation in science journalism. Q&A and interactive sessions were integrated into both the live and virtual components of the event. This communication approach not only facilitated real-time feedback but also empowered the co-creation process adopted during the whole project's lifetime.

The visual identity for the final events, in coherence with ENJOI's image, became a recognisable visual landmark for speakers and participants.

A tailored social media strategy to promote the events was defined, to engage with a broad and diverse audience actively. Live-tweeting sessions weaved together conversations and helped create a clear online presence.

The ENJOI website and Observatory served as a comprehensive hub, offering a repository for information, live streaming, and post-event resources.

Implementing multimedia content also played a pivotal role in capturing and sustaining audience attention.

Overall, collaboration turned out to be a cornerstone of the communication and dissemination strategy, which was highly increased by the national and international communication activities of all the ENJOI partners.

4.1 Visual identity and communication materials

The visual identity for the final events was meticulously crafted in coherence with ENJOI's overall visual identity developed at the beginning of the project. The program, slides, rollup,

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and associated materials harmoniously converged to create a cohesive and engaging brand presence.

The program design showcased a clean layout with the ENJOI colour palette. Iconography and imagery were thoughtfully selected to convey engagement and innovation as key pillars of the project.

This visual identity not only served as a guide through the event but also as a powerful tool in conveying the event's mission - bringing journalism and innovation together in a visually compelling and stimulating narrative. All ENJOI communication and dissemination materials, together with the educational materials and the project branding, are gender inclusive.

Here is a summary of the communication materials produced following the ENJOI's final events visual identity:

1. Agendas
2. Letterhead for invitations
3. Banner for event registrations
4. Graphics for newsletters and website
5. Rollup
6. Slides template
7. ENJOI Manifesto (printed version)
8. ENJOI SPI (printed version)
9. ENJOI shopper (for the final event in Bolonia)
10. ENJOI background layer
11. Background pictures for live streaming
12. Social media card (speakers of DAY TWO)
13. ENJOI bookmark

4.2 Social media strategy

A tailored social media strategy was implemented for both the events in Brussels and Bolonia. The overarching goal of this strategy was not only to disseminate information about the events but also to create a dynamic and inclusive digital environment that catalysed discussions and fostered connections among different actors within the science journalism and science communication frameworks.

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The cornerstone of the strategy was strategic content creation. ACCC (in charge of the ENJOI social media strategy within WP8) and formicablu (ENJOI's coordinator) worked together to define a shared strategy. Formicablu took the responsibility of implementing this strategy with a dedicated person within the team, taking advantage of the group's knowledge of the science journalism and science communication environment at the national and international levels. The social media strategy covered a period of three months, from September 2023 to November 2023.

The main focus of ENJOI's overall social media strategy is X (formerly Twitter), as for now, it remains the most suitable social media to engage relevant stakeholders, from journalists to researchers to policymakers. The account @ENJOIproject was set up in February 2021 by ACCC.

Leveraging the two main ENJOI social media platforms, X (formerly Twitter) and LinkedIn, a diverse array of content formats was deployed. Engaging social media cards were developed to set the scene and spread invitations to the face-to-face events. At the same time, live-tweeting sessions provided real-time updates and encouraged audience interaction.

Engagement as a key asset of innovation was one of the main pillars of the whole ENJOI lifetime. This approach was also implemented in the social media strategy, designed to cultivate an active and participatory audience. Hashtags #scicomm and #Enjoi were used as unifying elements, threading conversations across platforms and allowing users to contribute to the larger discourse seamlessly. Collaboration emerged as a driving force behind the success of the social media strategy. Engaging with scientists, journalists, communicators, and key accounts of the European Commission not only expanded the event's reach but also added credibility and diversity to the narrative.

As shown below, analytics played a pivotal role in assessing the quality of the social media strategy, as well as the events themselves. Beyond the quantitative metrics, qualitative feedback provided invaluable insights into the audience's perception of the event.

In conclusion, the social media strategy implemented during the events, in particular the public conference in Bologna, contributed to transforming these gatherings into an interdisciplinary conversation about how to promote innovation for better science communication and journalism.

During both events in Brussels and Bolonia, the social media content developed for X (formerly Twitter) and LinkedIn can be gathered into 4 main categories:

- Posts aimed at informing about the event (date, time, location, programme, etc.)
Examples: <https://twitter.com/ENJOIproject/status/1713943596510871595>
<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7130967422739619840>
- Call to action: register for the event, follow the streaming, and register to the newsletter informing about the events. Examples:
<https://twitter.com/ENJOIproject/status/1717489735898214732>
<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7130493671598141440>
- Live-tweeting sessions to provide real-time updates about the events and encourage audience interaction. Example:
<https://twitter.com/ENJOIproject/status/1725149530385981827>
- Follow-up contents. Example:
<https://twitter.com/ENJOIproject/status/1727022356324110509>
<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7126260427637886978>

All the posts are available on X at [@ENJOIproject](https://twitter.com/ENJOIproject) and LinkedIn at [ENJOI - Engagement and Journalism Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication](https://www.linkedin.com/company/enjoi-engagement-and-journalism-innovation-for-outstanding-open-science-communication).

Specific threads about the event can be found following the hashtags #enjo and #scicomm. Below there are some other selected social media contents with the audience interaction and X's analytics for the period September - November 2023.

Nov 2023 • 30 days

TWEET HIGHLIGHTS

NOV 2023 SUMMARY

Tweet Impressions
20.5K

Oct 2023 • 31 days

TWEET HIGHLIGHTS

OCT 2023 SUMMARY

Tweet Impressions
9,327

Sep 2023 • 30 days

TWEET HIGHLIGHTS

SEP 2023 SUMMARY

Tweet Impressions
2,386

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ENJOI project @ENJOIproject

"The Commission proposed to build a transparent publication platform. If you have some results to publish, you can do it with us."

Aleksandra Hebda

@OpenResearch_EU @HorizonEU @EU_Commission

11:21 am · 4 Oct 2023 · 50 Views

ENJOI project @ENJOIproject

Still grateful for energies and insights of yesterday's policy event in Brussels 🙏

Collected inputs will feed the final ENJOI policy brief, to help policy shape great science communication.

Another thanks to all the participants!

#enjo #scicomm

6:19 pm · 5 Oct 2023 · 93 Views

ENJOI project @ENJOIproject

Did you miss our final events in Bologna? Remember that you can retrieve them on ENJOI's YouTube channel ☺ at the following links!

16 Nov: youtube.com/live/bYxbQJKm...

17 Nov: youtube.com/live/GWFW7jT1...

#ENJOI #scicomm

6:53 pm · 21 Nov 2023 · 369 Views

View post engagements

ENJOI project @ENJOIproject

Participate in our Policy Event "Ethics, engagement and excellence: how can policy shape great #SciComm?" in Brussels on October 4th, at 10.30 CET. You can also follow it in our YouTube channel! youtube.com/channel/UCJXJA... cc @fornicablu @ACCC @stickydoteu @WFSJ @Science4Change

11:54 pm · 29 Sep 2023 · 2,820 Views

ENJOI project @ENJOIproject

We promised you to share the detailed programme of our final event in Bologna and here we are!

Two days, November 16th and 17th. The first one is reserved to our partners, while you are all invited to the November 17th meeting, which will be open to the public.

#scicomm #enjo

12:33 pm · 26 Oct 2023 · 2,861 Views

View post engagements

ENJOI project @ENJOIproject

Before the mid-morning break, the first roundtable of the day!

@stephanehorel, @albertotopi and @zsenteK, moderated by @kamatozinhos, will be main characters of the panel titled "Making journalism through collaboration and engagement".

#ENJOI #scicomm

12:37 pm · 9 Nov 2023 · 701 Views

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4.3 Website and Newsletter

The ENJOI [website](#) and [Observatory](#) served as a comprehensive hub, offering a repository for information, live streaming, and post-event resources. In particular, 4 news were disseminated through the ENJOI website and Observatory:

- *ENJOI Policy Event. Ethics, engagement and excellence: how can policy shape great science communication?* (September 2023). The article displayed all the useful information about the policy event in Brussels, including the registration form. It was spread through the ENJOI social media and newsletter.
<https://enjoiscicomm.eu/enjoi-policy-event-ethics-engagement-and-excellence-how-can-policy-shape-great-science-communication/>
- *Watch the ENJOI Policy Event: How can policy shape great science communication?* (October 2023). The article collected the main results and shared the full recording of the event. It was spread through the ENJOI social media and newsletter.
<https://enjoiscicomm.eu/watch-the-enjoi-policy-event-how-can-policy-shape-great-science-communication/>
- *ENJOI Final Event. Engagement and journalism innovation for outstanding open science communication.* (October 2023). The article displayed all the useful information about the first day of the final event in Bologna, including registration form. It was spread through the ENJOI social media and newsletter.
<https://enjoiscicomm.eu/enjoi-final-event-engagement-and-journalism-innovation-for-outstanding-open-science-communication/>
- *ENJOI Final Event. Innovation and engagement on the journalism horizon.* (October 2023). The article displayed all the useful information about the first day of the final event in Bologna, including registration form. It was spread through the ENJOI social media and newsletter.
<https://enjoiscicomm.eu/enjoi-final-event-innovation-and-engagement-on-the-journalism-horizon/>

Besides these articles, two specific newsletter issues were prepared and spread to promote the events. During the first project period, an ENJOI community was built through the involvement of all stakeholders who took part in activities such as the ENJOI Engagement workshops (EWs) and Labs. Participants engaged during the ENJOI events and workshops expressed a strong interest in participating in the ENJOI Observatory. This led the consortium to the planning of an ENJOI newsletter as an extra communication activity, which was kicked off in 2023 and will continue beyond the project's end.

The two newsletter issues focused on the policy event and final event, respectively, and were sent out to invite subscribers to register and/or follow the live streaming of the events. A recap of the newsletter performance is available below. These contents were also spread through the partners' newsletters and channels (in particular, ACCC and formicablu).

ENJOI Observatory Newsletter #2: Policy Event, 4 October, Brussels Sent 9/22/23 3:05AM

Overview

42 Recipients

Audience: ENJOI **Delivered:** Fri, Sep 22, 2023 3:05 AM

Subject: ENJOI Observatory Newsletter
#2: Policy Event, 4 October, Brussels

24 Opened	4 Clicked	1 Bounced	0 Unsubscribed
---------------------	---------------------	---------------------	--------------------------

Successful deliveries	41	97.6%	Clicks per unique opens	16.7%
Total opens	39		Total clicks	11
Last opened	10/10/23 9:04AM		Last clicked	9/25/23 4:23AM

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ENJOI Observatory Newsletter #3: ENJOI Final Event, 17 November, Sent 11/3/23 11:01AM
Bologna

Overview

68 Recipients

Audience: ENJOI

Delivered: Fri, Nov 3, 2023 11:01 AM

Subject: ENJOI Observatory Newsletter
#3: ENJOI Final Event, 17 November,
Bologna

44 Opened	12 Clicked	1 Bounced	0 Unsubscribed
---------------------	----------------------	---------------------	--------------------------

Successful deliveries	67 98.5%	Clicks per unique opens	27.3%
Total opens	102	Total clicks	27
Last opened	12/6/23 8:53AM	Last clicked	11/10/23 2:12PM

All the main final events-related content disseminated through the ENJOI website and newsletter was also shared with relevant EC services, such as Cordis, Horizon Magazine, DG Research & Innovation contacts, etc. The European Commission's support was crucial to help spread information about the ENJOI events (see example below).

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Horizon Europe

@HorizonEU

Follow the event on 16 & 17 Nov to learn how the EU-funded @ENJOIproject fights #FakeNews with #OpenScience communication.

⚠ Spoiler alert: Quality journalism helps to stop misinformation from undermining citizens' ability to tackle problems & democracy as a whole.

ENJOI project @ENJOIproject · 14 Nov

We are now very close to our final event in Bologna!

You can also follow the 16 and 17 November event online, via live streaming on YouTube.

...

[Show more](#)

|| GIF ALT

4:58 pm · 14 Nov 2023 · 5,086 Views

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4.4 Video Production

Implementing multimedia content played a pivotal role in capturing and sustaining audience attention. Engaging videos featuring snippets of panel discussions, interviews with keynote speakers, and behind-the-scenes glimpses provided a dynamic visual experience.

Exclusive interviews with event speakers enriched the narrative, tapping into established networks and bringing a diverse array of perspectives to the forefront.

Post-event resources, including multimedia products (see 4.4) will continue feeding the ENJOI Observatory and will be spread through the ENJOI Newsletter.

Here below is the list of the **19 videos** produced and that will be available on ENJOI's YouTube channel:

1. The policy event in a nutshell
2. Enjoi final event suggestions
3. How do you think journalism could be improved in the present day?
4. Interview to Zeynep Sentek
5. Interview with Stephane Horel
6. Interview with Sofia Da Palma Rodriguez
7. Interview with Priti Patnaik
8. Interview with Raffaele Angius
9. Interview with Michael Creek
10. Interview with Alberto Pulafito
11. Interview with Michele Catanzaro
12. Interview with Eva Rodriguez
13. Interview with Anne Dijkstra
14. Interview with Aron Pilhofer
15. Interview with Marco Boscolo
16. Interview with Davide Del Monte
17. Interview with Esther Marin
18. Interview with Anna Violato
19. Interview with Elisabetta Tola

4.5 KPIs

A set of success communication indicators (KPIs) was defined in the ENJOI Communication and Dissemination Plan (D8.1). These indicators were the basis for constantly monitoring whether the communication objectives were being met, thus allowing a periodic revision of the ENJOI communication strategy. The KPIs were also used to evaluate the success of the communication and dissemination strategy of the final events, as the table below shows.

TOOL	KPI	Expected M36	Status after final events
Project website	SEO insights (Matomo)	5,000 visits	4,494
	Outlinks	500	342
	Mobile Performance Analysis	50%	66,9%
X	Followers	600	1,214
	Impressions	5,000	20,000
LinkedIn	Followers	200	180
	Impressions (last year)	1,000	1,628
Newsletter Posts	N° of posts/news distributed through Newsletters	6+	8 (3 ENJOI Newsletter + 5 partners' newsletters)

Table 1 - ENJOI KPI for final events

ANNEX

Contents:

1. Agendas
2. Letterhead for invitations
3. Banner for event registrations
4. Graphics for newsletters and website
5. Rollup
6. Slides template
7. ENJOI Manifesto (printed version)
8. ENJOI SPI (printed version)
9. ENJOI shopper (for the final event in Bolonia)
10. Background layer
11. Background pictures for live streaming
12. Social media cards (speakers of DAY TWO)
13. ENJOI bookmark

1. Agendas

a. DAY ONE

ENJOI ENJOI FINAL EVENT
Engagement and Journalism
Innovation for Outstanding
Open Science Communication

16 NOVEMBER 2023
Palazzo Pepoli Museum,
Via Castiglione 10,
Bologna

14:00 - 14:30 Registration

14:30 - 14:50 Welcome and introduction. The ENJOI pathway
Elisabetta Tola,
ENJOI coordinator,
formicablu, Italy

14:50 - 15:10 The ENJOI SPIs and the Manifesto
Michele Catanzaro,
Asociación Catalana de Comunicación Científica, Spain

15:10 - 15:40 The ENJOI Observatory.
Innovation, engagement and openness in science journalism
Marco Boscolo and Giulia Bonelli,
formicablu, Italy

15:40 - 16:00 Science, media relationship: research findings
Anne Dijkstra and Anouk de Jong,
University of Twente, Netherlands

16:00 - 16:30 Coffee break

16:30 - 17:00 The ENJOI co-creation process: what did we learn?
Michael Creek,
Stickydot, Belgium
Karinna Matozinhos,
Science for Change, Spain

17:00 - 17:20 Innovative tools for multiple target users, an ENJOI production
Esther Marín,
FCiências.ID, Associação para a Investigação e
Desenvolvimento de Ciências, Portugal

17:20 - 17:40 Recommendations for an Outstanding Open Science Communication
Elisabetta Tola,
formicablu, Italy

17:40 - 18:10 What will you take from the ENJOI project?
Moderated by Michael Creek,
Stickydot, Belgium

18:10 - 18:30 What next? ENJOI and COALESCE
Joana Magalhães,
Science for Change, Spain
Elisabetta Tola,
formicablu, Italy

Funded by the European Union

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b. DAY TWO

The poster features a teal header with the ENJOI logo and event title. An orange circle in the top right corner contains the date and location. The main body is yellow with a list of sessions in teal boxes. A stylized graphic of a hand holding a pencil is in the top right, and a starburst graphic with the event name is in the bottom right. The European Union logo and funding information are at the bottom left.

ENJOI ENJOI FINAL EVENT
Innovation and engagement on the journalism horizon

17 NOVEMBER 2023
Palazzo Pepoli Museum,
Via Castiglione 10,
Bologna

9:00 – 9:30 Registration

9:30 – 9:40 Welcome from the ENJOI Coordinator
Elisabetta Tola - *formicablu*

9.40 - 10.20 Innovation and sustainability in journalism today
Aron Pilhofer, James B. Steel Chair in Journalism Innovation, Temple University

10.20 - 10.40 Q&A with Aron Pilhofer
Moderator: Giulia Bonelli - *formicablu*

10.40 - 11.10 Roundtable 1, Making journalism through collaboration and engagement
Stephane Horel - *Le Monde, France*
Alberto Puliafito - *Slow News, Italy*
Zeynep Sentek - coordinator of *The toxic Valley* investigative project and director of the *Arena Climate Network, Turkey and Portugal*
Moderator: Karinna Matozinhos - *Science for Change*

11.10 - 1.40 Coffee and networking

11.40 - 12.10 Roundtable 2, Diving into in depth journalism
Raffaele Angius - *Indip, IRPImedia, Italy*
Sofia da Palma Rodrigues - *Divergente, Portugal*
Eva Rodriguez - *SINC, Spain*
Moderator: Michele Catanzaro - *Asociación Catalana de Comunicación Científica*

12.10 - 12.20 Broadening the definition of journalism. A few stories
Moderator: Marco Boscolo - *formicablu*

12.20 - 12.30 Info.nodes and Marla. Between activism and journalism
Davide Del Monte - *Italy*

12.30 - 12.40 Geneva Health Files. Health information in your mailbox
Priti Patnaik - *Switzerland*

12.40 - 12.50 Radar. A new look to environment
Anna Violato - *Italy*

12.50 - 13.00 Thin Ink. Deep into the food world
Thin Lei Win - *Birmanla, Italy*

13.00 - 13.30 Wrap up
Elisabetta Tola - *formicablu*

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2. Letterhead for invitations

a. DAY ONE

b. DAY TWO

3. Banner for event registrations

a. DAY ONE

**Engagement and Journalism Innovation
for Outstanding Open Science
Communication ENJOI Final Event
REGISTRATION**

ENJOI - Engagement and JOURNALISM Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication

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b. DAY TWO

Innovation and engagement on the journalism horizon ENJOI Final Event registration

c. Museum guided tour registration

ENJOI Final Event, **MUSEUM GUIDED TOUR**

d. Dietary restrictions

ENJOI Final Event **DIETARY RESTRICTIONS**

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4. ENJOI Newsletter and Website

a. ENJOI Newsletter (#3)

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b. ENJOI Website

The homepage

The SPIs page

The project structure

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The ENJOI Observatory page

The ENJOi Magazine

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5. ENJOI Roll up

A vertical graphic for the ENJOI project. The top half has a teal background with the word 'ENJOI' in large white letters, where the 'J' is a pencil. Below it is the text 'Engagement And Journalism Innovation For Outstanding Open Science Communication.' The middle section contains three bullet points: 'Improving #scicomm and #journalism by making them more consistently, reliable, truthful, open, engaging and useful.', 'Contributing to the development of critical thinking.', and 'Raise digital awareness.' To the right of these points is an illustration of colorful stick figures and lightbulbs. The bottom half has a yellow background with a large white pencil shape on the right. It contains the hashtag '#scicomm', the website 'www.enjoiscicomm.eu', and the Twitter handle '@ENJOIproject'. At the bottom left is the European Union flag and a small text block: 'ENJOI - Engagement and Journalism Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication. This project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under Grant Agreement n°101006407'.

ENJOI

**Engagement And Journalism Innovation
For Outstanding Open Science Communication.**

Improving #scicomm
and #journalism by
making them more
consistently, reliable,
truthful, open,
engaging and useful.

Contributing to
the development
of critical thinking.

Raise digital awareness.

#scicomm
www.enjoiscicomm.eu

 @ENJOIproject

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6. Slides template

ENJOI

ENJOI FINAL EVENT
Engagement and Journalism
Innovation for Outstanding
Open Science Communication

ENJOI FINAL EVENT

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7. ENJOI Manifesto (printed version)

ENJOI

MANIFESTO FOR OUTSTANDING OPEN SCIENCE COMMUNICATION

A simple guide for science communicators, journalists, researchers, citizens.

DEEPENING THE ROOTS

The future growth of science communication depends on the strength of its roots, especially in contexts where they are challenged by the fragility of the media ecosystem. Independence, transparency, integrity, transparency, rigor, and the use of independent and diverse research are basic principles of high-quality, evidence-based, and trustworthy communication that researchers and non-researchers.

Creating an inclusive ecosystem of information. Good engagement goes beyond one-way feedback. It requires building a true collaborative framework, not a talking community that takes part in a two-way dialogue.

This implies focusing not only on content, but also on the process behind it, and the enabling conditions of science with society. Successful science communication should respond to the rights and interests of citizens, and not to other interests. Openness is implemented into a variety of niches.

BEARING NEW FRUITS

ENJOI envisions a set of trends that are likely to occur in the future of science communication. These trends are not new, but they require a critical stance, between they pose both challenges and opportunities. Science communication happens increasingly in digital platforms, especially in social media. The emergence of digital natives and digital citizens are shaped by digital natives, with artificial intelligence, reality, and metrics. Responsibility and ethics take a very important role.

It is crucial to understand these trends and foster communication through a variety of strategies suitable for each type of user. It is especially important to make science accessible to audiences traditionally with a hard-to-disseminate group.

Science communication is relevant if it generates an impact, which can range from awareness to action. Tools to people and improve this impact are increasingly important in this craft.

A LIVING DOCUMENT

The ideas outlined in this manifesto are proposed on the table, open and require and represent the foundations of the ENJOI Living Document. These roots are aimed at applying the science of the manifesto in the teaching, research, and practice of science communication.

The manifesto is not written in stone. It is an open-ended, living document that will be revised with our advisory board, experts, and engaged communities.

We hope this text will provide a solid and fertile ground for the practice of the science communication that open.

Inclusion is cutting through all aspects of science communication. In doing so, it connects with the past, recognizing diversity is set to become a guiding principle, not just in formal and linguistic terms, but at deeper levels, from the practice of science to the ways contents are distributed.

The spaces of health and environmental ethics are fertile on science. However, open to the public, science communication is likely to explore more often the possible courses of action.

The spirit of open science is reimagining science communication that, not only with special attention to open access journals, but also with a broader commitment towards making science communication that open.

WHAT
Provide a set of trends, principles and indicators, and tools to support science communication in practice, and to people in areas of continuing and changing scientific information.

WHERE
This Manifesto: Open Manifesto for Outstanding Open Science Communication for Outstanding Open Science Communication.

WHEN
This project (2021-2023) and its heritage in the ENJOI Community beyond the project lifetime.

WHY
With a particular focus on the European Union, ENJOI aims to address the challenges of science communication and to provide a living document.

WHO
ENJOI Portugal, ENJOI Europe, and leading experts in science, research, journalism, and communication as stakeholders.

Coauthors:
Parvaneh - Institute for Science Communication (ISC) - University of Lisbon
Stefano - Institute for Science Communication (ISC) - University of Lisbon
Stefano - Institute for Science Communication (ISC) - University of Lisbon

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© ENJOI project
Donors: ENJOI SciComm
info@enjoiscicomm.eu

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8. The ENJOI SPIs (printed version)

Cover of the ENJOI SPIs brochure

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The ENJOI SPIS brochure table of contents:

- What are the SPIS
- ENJOI's Principles
- ENJOI's Standards
- ENJOI's Indicators

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9. ENJOI Shoppers

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10. Background layer

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11. Background images for live streaming

DAY ONE

DAY TWO

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12. Social media cards

a. Final event cards (DAY ONE & DAY TWO)

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b. Speakers' social cards (DAY TWO)

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Via Castiglione 10,
Bologna
enjoiscicomm.eu

ELISABETTA TOLA
ENJOI coordinator
formicablu | ITALY

Science, data and tech journalist.
CEO of formicablu and founder of Facta.eu.
Chief editor at Il Bo Live, presenter and
author at Radio3Scienza.

TALK:
Innovation and engagement on the journalism
horizon: Welcome & wrap up

Funded by
the European Union

#ENJOI #scicomm @elisabetta_tola

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ARON PILHOFFER
Temple University | us

James B. Steele Chair in Journalism
Innovation at Temple University. Former
Executive Editor, Digital, and interim Chief
Digital Officer at the Guardian and Associate
Managing Editor for Digital Strategy and editor
of Interactive News at The New York Times.

TALK:
Innovation and sustainability
in journalism today

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#ENJOI #scicomm @pilhofer

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STEPHANE HOREL
Le Monde | FRANCE

Investigative journalist at Le Monde,
specialised in corporate lobbying
and harm, conflict of interest
and scientific disinformation.

ROUNDTABLE:
Making journalism through
collaboration and engagement

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#ENJOI #scicomm @stephanehorel

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Bologna
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ALBERTO PULIAFITO
Slow News | ITALY

Journalist specialized in digital tools,
an innovation consultant and a SEO expert.
Founder of Slow News, an online project
of slow journalism.

ROUNDTABLE:
Making journalism through
collaboration and engagement

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#ENJOI #scicomm @albertopi

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**ZEYNEP
SENTEK**

**Arena Climate Network
TURKEY & PORTUGAL**

Investigative journalist, Coordinator of
The toxic Valley investigative project
and director of the Arena Climate Network.

ROUNDTABLE:
Making journalism through
collaboration and engagement

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#ENJOI #scomm

zsentek

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16 - 17 NOVEMBER 2023
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Via Castiglione 10,
Bologna

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**KARINNA
MATOZINHOS**

Science for Change | SPAIN

Communication expert, marketing
strategic officer and project manager at
Science for Change, a social enterprise
in Barcelona that promotes collaborative
research, evidence-informed public policy
and quality scientific communication.

ROUNDTABLE:
Making journalism through
collaboration and engagement

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#ENJOI #scomm

@kamatozinhos

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Bologna

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**RAFFAELE
ANGIUS**

IrpiMedia | ITALY

Journalist at IrpiMedia and co-founder
of the independent investigative
magazine Indip, working mainly on
surveillance technologies, source
protection, environmental investigations
and organised crime.

ROUNDTABLE:
Diving into in depth journalism

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#ENJOI #scomm

faffa42

ENJOI FINAL EVENT

16 - 17 NOVEMBER 2023
Palazzo Pepoli Museum,
Via Castiglione 10,
Bologna

ENJOI
enjoiscicomm.eu

**SOFIA DA PALMA
RODRIGUES**

Divergente | PORTUGAL

Journalist with experience as
investigative reporter in different
countries and co-founder of Divergente,
an independent magazine of
narrative journalism in Lisbon.

ROUNDTABLE:
Diving into in depth journalism

Funded by
the European Union

#ENJOI #scomm

spalmarodrigues

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Via Castiglione 10,
Bologna

ENJOI
enjoiscicomm.eu

**EVA RODRIGUEZ
NIETO**

Agencia Sinc | SPAIN

Journalist specialised in science,
environment and society at The SINC
agency (Servicio de Información y Noticias
Científicas), the scientific news agency
of the Spanish Foundation for Science
and Technology.

ROUNDTABLE:
Diving into in depth journalism

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the European Union

#ENJOI #scomm

@evaou22

ENJOI FINAL EVENT

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Palazzo Pepoli Museum,
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Bologna

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**MICHELE
CATANZARO**

ACCC | SPAIN

Journalist and lecturer based in Barcelona,
writing mainly about science, environment,
and health for outlets like: Nature, Science,
El Periódico, Süddeutsche Zeitung,
Der Spiegel, The Guardian, Repubblica.it,
Le Scienze, and others.

ROUNDTABLE:
Diving into in depth journalism

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the European Union

#ENJOI #scomm

@mcatanzaro

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Via Castiglione 10,
Bologna

enjoiscicomm.eu

DAVIDE DEL MONTE

info.nodes | ITALY

Transparency and anti-corruption expert, an activist and a researcher. Founder of info.nodes, an editorial project to support journalists and activists who want to run investigations and expose the truth.

TALK:
Info.nodes and Marla.
Between activism and journalism

 Funded by the European Union
 #ENJOI #scicomm @davidovskij

ENJOI FINAL EVENT

16 - 17 NOVEMBER 2023
Palazzo Pepoli Museum,
Via Castiglione 10,
Bologna

enjoiscicomm.eu

PRITI PATNAIK

Geneva Health Files | SWITZERLAND

Journalist and founder of Geneva Health Files, a journalistic endeavour reporting global health developments. Previously worked as a journalist for twenty years in Geneva, New York and New Delhi.

TALK:
Geneva Health Files.
Health information in your mailbox

 Funded by the European Union
 #ENJOI #scicomm @pretpat

ENJOI FINAL EVENT

16 - 17 NOVEMBER 2023
Palazzo Pepoli Museum,
Via Castiglione 10,
Bologna

enjoiscicomm.eu

ANNA VIOLATO

Radar Magazine | ITALY

Science editor and author at Radar Magazine. Collaborating with Nature Italy, formicablu and others.

TALK:
Radar. A new look to environment

 Funded by the European Union
 #ENJOI #scicomm anna_violato

ENJOI FINAL EVENT

16 - 17 NOVEMBER 2023
Palazzo Pepoli Museum,
Via Castiglione 10,
Bologna

enjoiscicomm.eu

THIN LEI WIN

Thin Ink | ITALY

Journalist with extensive experience reporting on humanitarian issues. Founder of Thin Ink, a weekly newsletter on the intersection of food systems and climate change.

TALK:
Thin Ink. Deep into the food world

 Funded by the European Union
 #ENJOI #scicomm think

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13.ENJOI bookmark

Front

Back

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